

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE SYSTEM OF ORGANIZING AND OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT OF LABOR PROTECTION AT ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: In this article, an innovative approach to the organization of labor protection in enterprises and increasing the effectiveness of the operational management system, digitization of the operational technologies of the management process, the development of a practical program of IT information technologies and the introduction of them into the fields, measures aimed at restoring the health, safety and work ability of employees during the work process. The possibility of increasing the economic efficiency of the decisions made on.

Keywords: labor protection, labor protection management, occupational diseases, accidents, innovative approach, safety policy.

Introduction. The Regulation on the procedure for the development and organization of the labor protection service in organizations was approved by the Cabinet of Ministers, as is well known. It should be mentioned that this position was established or introduced in an obligatory manner to control the completion of legal document requirements and to guarantee compliance with them [1]. The duties and responsibilities of the organization's labor protection service, as well as the rights and responsibilities of the head of the service and service personnel, are outlined in this regulation. It also specifies the prerequisites for the head of the service and specialists. The primary objective of the general requirements for the labor protection management system (GOST 12.0.230-2007, GOST R ISO 45001-2020) is to help safeguard employees against the consequences of hazardous and detrimental production factors, accidents, and occupational diseases, including the exclusion of death [2–3].

Methods. The organization and management system of labor protection in businesses encompasses the processes of action on labor protection and safety policy, organization, planning and financing, evaluation, and improvement, as per the guidelines of GOST 12.0.230-2007 and GOST R ISO 45001-2020 [2–3]. Receiving, storing, analyzing, transferring, and making pertinent, significant judgments based on a vast amount of diverse information are all necessary steps in carrying out these procedures (Fig. 1).

The standards provide a detailed description of the work that is done within the framework of the labor protection and safety policy, organization, planning and financing, evaluation, and improvement processes related to the organization and management of labor protection in the enterprise, the

organization and management system of labor protection in enterprises GOST 12.0.230-2007, GOST R ISO 45001-2020. These sub-processes in turn require receiving, storing, processing, and transmitting information, drawing decisions quickly based on those conclusions, and making significant management decisions (Fig. 2)[2–4].

Figure 1. The main elements of the labor protection and safety management system.

It is well known that labor protection is entering a new era of innovation in the twenty-first century. At this point, it is necessary to concentrate on developing safety systems and tools based on modern technologies, automation, artificial intelligence, and IT technologies, developing a safety culture in production processes, and improving management systems. Researching the safety of production technologies, predicting and preventing risks, ensuring that workers comply with ergonomic requirements, lowering workers' psychological states and stress levels, preventing occupational fatigue, nervous tension, and other psychological factors, and improving workplace hygiene conditions, prevention of damage, maintenance of health of workers in the working environment, chemical, physical and biological protection from risks, national and international legislation on labor safety, research and implementation of regulatory documents, responsibility of employers for labor protection and protection of workers' rights, management of risks arising from the introduction of modern technologies, digital technologies conducting research on security issues (for example, cyberthreats) related to [5-6]. By studying these problems, the development of labor protection and the practical application of innovative solutions will be further improved.

Research is necessary to address the issues pertaining to the innovative stage of labor protection mentioned above, such as workplace ergonomics compliance, worker psychological well-being and stress reduction, prevention of occupational fatigue, nervous tension, and other psychological factors, and safety issues with digital technologies (like cyberthreats)[8]. To a certain degree, this problem can be resolved by improving the effectiveness of the operational management system and organizing labor protection in businesses in a novel way [9]. In turn, resolving the issue of precisely calculating the amount of information transmitted in this system is strongly tied to the creative approach to labor protection organization in businesses and to improving the efficacy of the operational management system [10].

Figure 2. Information-sharing operational technology used in the company's labor protection management and organization procedures

Result. Information is fundamental to all "human-technology-environmental system" management activities, including information reception, processing, decision-making, and transfer of control actions to controlling authorities. One cannot compare the speed at which a computer processes information to that of a human. The labor protection officer enters 90% of the data when working with EHM using words and symbols, and 10% using actions. Additionally, EHM gives people 95% of their knowledge through sight, 4% through hearing, and 1% through other means [7].

There are three primary components to the information transfer problem:

Choosing the physical alphabet of signals aimed at an individual is the psychophysical component (task: to ensure the optimal detection of signals).

The theoretical-information component evaluates the maximum amount of information that can be received and processed in a given amount of time (tasks include figuring out the ideal signal alphabet length, assessing the "saturation" of signals with information, evaluating the number of timely distributions of a specific amount of information, and determining the necessary dimensions (properties).

The study of psychological processes by which an individual receives and processes information is known as the psychological aspect (task: decoding incoming information and constructing a subjective image of a signal).

Signals are separated into two categories: symbolic signals and image signals. The former indicate the attributes of the item.

The ability of the labor protection employee to receive and process information must be checked as well as quantitatively evaluated for the "Human-Technology-Environment System" to function steadily and smoothly. It is found using mathematical information theory. It makes it possible to ascertain how much of each kind of data the operator processes. The bit (from the English language: binary + digit = a binary character) is the unit of measure for the amount of information. The following calculation determines how much information the labor protection officer in the control panel has received overall:

$$I_{worker}^{overall} = I_{tk} + I_y + I_{ovoz} + I_h + I_a, \text{ byte}$$

There I_{tk} – the amount of information received through image display devices (television, monitor, screen, scoreboard, etc.) is determined according to the following formula.

$$I_{tk} = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^K n \cdot \log_2 N, \text{ byte}$$

where t - is the time of information transmission (reception);

n -the number of measured parameters of control points;

N -message alphabet length;

$i=1, 2, \dots, K$ -number of transmitted messages.

The amount of written information (telegrams, orders, faxes) received by the I_y -Labor protection officer is determined according to the following formula:

$$I_y = m_h \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N P_i, \text{ byte}$$

m_h - the number of letters or numbers in the message;

N - the length of the message alphabet;

P_i - probability of i -letter or number appearing in the message.

I_n -The amount of speech data received through voice communication channels (oral, telephone) is determined by the following formula:

$$I_n = F_s \cdot \sum_{i=1}^F P_i \cdot \log_2 P_i, \text{ byte}$$

$$I_n = F_s \cdot f_{av}.$$

F_s – the number of sounds in the message (Phoneme—sound unit of spoken speech);

f_{av} –average precision for each phoneme. It depends on the message type and ranges from 0.094 to 0.3 byte/phoneme. For experimental calculations, its maximum value is accepted.

I_a – additional information used for decision-making (instructions, technological processes, rules of use, etc.);

I_h – the amount of data lost during transmission through communication channels.

For the agreed acceptance and processing of information, the condition of the agreement must be fulfilled:

$$I_{tk} \leq I_{xodim}^{umumiy}$$

If this condition is not met, the labor protection officer will not be able to process the incoming data within a certain time.

The amount of information provided per time unit (byte/sec) is determined by the formula:

$$H = \frac{I_{xodim}^{umumiy}}{t_{uz}}, \text{ byte/sec}$$

t_{uz} – message transmission duration in seconds.

The amount of data that a human operator receives and processes is called its throughput.

$$C = \frac{n \cdot \log_2 N}{T_k}$$

Here n – the number of correctly marked characters,

T_k – time of providing, transmitting or displaying information, sec.

The first law of ergonomics:

$$H \leq C$$

here H – the flow of information to the labor protection officer;

C - capabilities of the labor protection officer.

Discussion. The results depend on the capabilities of the labor protection officer (C), the type of problem being solved, the degree of participation of the labor protection officer in the operation of the measurement system, the quality of data visualization, including the brightness, contrast, character size and alphabet length of the monitors, etc. liq. The speed of human information acquisition is 10-70 bits/s and largely depends on the type of activity. The experimentally obtained values of human information acquisition speed in bit/s, according to the type of activity are as follows: reading text "for yourself" - 45; reading aloud - 30; assembly work-18; typewriter-16; adding two numbers - 12; multiplication of two numbers - 12; product count or account-3.

The amount of different kinds of information that the operator processes in the innovative approach to labor protection organization and the effectiveness of the operational management system in businesses can be ascertained in this sequence. The problem of precise calculation is resolved in the innovative approach to labor protection organization in businesses and the effectiveness of the operational management system to increase the volume of information moving in this system. This makes it feasible to precisely compute the information flow and volume exchanged in the operational management technology stages (Fig. 3), where a variety of tasks are carried out by experts in the primary phases of the labor protection and safety management system.

Figure 3. Operational technology of operational management

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that an innovative approach to the organization of labor protection in enterprises and to increase the effectiveness of the operative management system is based on the capabilities of the human element in the "human-technology-environmental system" system, that is, the ability of a person to receive and process information. , storage, transmission and related decision-making are limited by the speed in bt/s. As a result, some of the measures implemented by the labor protection organization and operative management system in the enterprises are being implemented late and in the end do not give the expected positive results.

It will be possible to increase the economic efficiency of the decisions made on the targeted activities by taking an innovative approach to organizing labor protection in enterprises, increasing the efficiency of the operational management system, digitizing the operational technologies of the management process (Fig. 3), developing an application program for IT information technologies, and implementing them in the fields. These measures will help to restore the health, safety, and work ability of employees in the work process.

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